

A Study on Decline of Foundries in Coimbatore

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Abstract

The foundry industry in Coimbatore, once a major hub for cast metal production in South India, has witnessed a significant decline over the past decade. This study investigates the key factors contributing to the downturn of foundries in the region and identifies viable strategies for revival. Based on responses from stakeholders through a structured questionnaire, the research highlights the impact of rising raw material and energy costs, regulatory pressures, labor shortages, and market volatility. It also outlines actionable strategies such as policy interventions, technology adoption, and financial support mechanisms to rejuvenate the sector.

Keywords: Foundries, Coimbatore, Industrial Decline, Challenges, Revival Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Coimbatore, popularly known as the "Manchester of South India," has historically been a crucial industrial hub, playing a pivotal role in India's manufacturing landscape. One of its most significant contributors has been the foundry industry, which serves as the backbone for sectors like automotive, agriculture, construction, textile machinery, and pump manufacturing. The foundries in Coimbatore have traditionally been known for their technical capabilities, entrepreneurial vigor, and employment generation, with over 500 registered units operating at the industry's peak. These foundries not only contributed substantially to the local economy but also played a key role in positioning Coimbatore as a global supplier of high-quality castings. The cluster model, skilled labor availability, and access to local engineering talent helped Coimbatore foundries thrive for decades. However, the last 10–15 years have seen a noticeable and worrying downturn in this once-flourishing industry. A significant number of small and medium foundries have either shut down or are operating far below their capacity.

Several interlinked factors have contributed to this decline. These include escalating costs of raw materials and power, stricter environmental regulations, shortage of skilled labor, lack of access to modern technology, financial stress, and increasing global competition. Compounding these are macroeconomic challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic, changing demand patterns, and disruption of supply chains.

This study aims to investigate the root causes of the decline, understand the perspectives of key stakeholders, and assess the operational and policy-related challenges affecting the sector. It also seeks to identify feasible strategies—ranging from modernization, skill development, policy reform, to financial restructuring—that can rejuvenate the foundry ecosystem in Coimbatore. A deeper understanding of these issues is essential to formulate targeted interventions that can help sustain and grow this crucial industry in the years ahead.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To identify the key challenges leading to the closure of foundries in Coimbatore.

To analyse the impact of regulatory, economic, and operational issues on foundry operations.

To explore stakeholders' perceptions and insights on the current state and future prospects of the industry.

To recommend strategic interventions for the revival of the foundry sector in Coimbatore.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ramasamy, K. (2015) study provides a regional breakdown of foundry operations across India and identifies Coimbatore as a high-risk zone due to outdated technologies and lack of policy intervention.¹

Bharathi, S. & Kumar, M. (2016) research highlights rising energy costs, labor issues, and regulatory delays as key hurdles affecting foundries, particularly in Tamil Nadu.²

Gupta, A. & Roy, T. (2018) paper details how lack of working capital and limited access to institutional finance affects small foundries and MSMEs.³

Institute of Indian Foundrymen (IIF) Annual Report (2019) The IIF report discusses nationwide trends and data showing that 30% of foundries have shut down due to compliance costs and poor returns on investment.⁴

Sundararajan, R. (2017) explores how newer environmental laws disproportionately affect small and medium enterprises like foundries.⁵

Chakraborty, N. (2020) presents a broader perspective on industrial clusters and points out the decline in Coimbatore's competitiveness due to lack of innovation.⁶

KPMG India Report (2021)

industry report includes a section on casting and foundry challenges, mentioning capacity underutilization, increased global competition, and inconsistent demand.⁷

Singh, P. & Sharma, L. (2019) study reveals that a majority of foundries are reluctant or unable to adopt new technologies due to high investment costs and limited technical training.⁸

Venkatesh, B. (2018) look at labor shortages and lack of technical training programs for foundry work, especially in the southern states.⁹

Ministry of MSME, Government of India (2020) report highlights the systemic neglect of traditional industries like foundries, citing that only 4% received modernization funding.¹⁰

NASSCOM-McKinsey Report (2017) while not specific to foundries, this report projects how automation and AI will displace traditional casting methods unless adaptation accelerates.¹¹

Ravichandran, T. (2016) highlights power shortages, poor logistics, and supply chain delays that contribute to the inefficiency of Coimbatore foundries.¹²

Krishna, H. & Mehta, D. (2015) points out that fluctuations in import/export duties affect raw material costs, severely impacting cost-sensitive industries like foundries.¹³

World Bank (2018) – "Ease of Doing Business in India: Sectoral Study" Ranks the foundry industry low in terms of ease of doing business due to licensing, taxation, and compliance burdens.¹⁴

Patel, R. & Deshmukh, S. (2022) examines the long-term effects of the pandemic on the foundry sector, especially with supply chain fragmentation and cash flow disruptions.¹⁵

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method: Descriptive research

Primary Data: Questionnaire to foundry owners and experts

Focus Areas: Costs, labor, policies, market, technology

Secondary Data: Reports, journals, and government documents

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Major Reasons for Closure:

Respondents identified rising raw material costs, energy shortages, and regulatory pressures as the primary reasons for closures. Specifically, 40% of participants indicated that the energy crisis had a significant impact, while 35% cited environmental regulations as a major challenge that was often costly and time-consuming to comply with.

Impact of Energy and Raw

Material Costs: A majority of respondents (around 65%) noted significant increases in electricity and fuel prices, along with the limited availability and rising cost of raw materials like scrap metal and coke. These factors disrupted operational continuity and directly reduced profit margins, forcing many small and medium-scale units to shut down.

Role of Government Policies and

Regulations: Respondents highlighted that strict environmental regulations and complex labor laws placed a heavy burden on operational viability. Many also expressed dissatisfactions with the lack of targeted policy support, tax relief, or incentives for energy efficiency improvements. Several industry participants noted that bureaucratic red tape delayed the implementation of modernization initiatives and discouraged investment.

Market and Demand Factors:

Declining demand from key industries such

as automotive, agriculture, and construction was identified as a major concern. Over 60% of participants mentioned a noticeable drop in orders due to shifting market demands, global competition, and the adoption of alternative materials by client sectors, which affected their ability to sustain operations.

Technological Obsolescence:

Many foundries acknowledged operating with outdated machinery and processes that limited productivity and product quality. The lack of access to affordable modern technology and technical know-how made it difficult for units to remain competitive. Respondents unanimously agreed that modernization and automation were essential for long-term survival, but cited capital constraints and knowledge gaps as major barriers.

Labor and Skill Shortages:

Labor availability was a significant concern for 55% of respondents. With increasing wage demands and a decline in the availability of skilled workers, many foundries struggled to maintain quality standards and meet production schedules. Additionally, younger workers were reportedly less interested in joining the foundry sector due to health risks and better opportunities elsewhere.

Financial Burden and Debt:

Approximately 50% of surveyed foundries reported facing significant financial distress. High interest rates on loans, delayed payments from clients, and poor cash flow management pushed many units into mounting debt. The absence of accessible and affordable financial assistance schemes further compounded the situation.

External and Global Factors:

Respondents also acknowledged that global disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical tensions, and import-export restrictions had adversely

impacted the supply of key materials and disrupted pricing. These macroeconomic challenges, combined with domestic issues, accelerated the decline of many foundries.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The decline in Coimbatore's foundry sector is the result of an interplay of multiple factors, both internal and external.

Core issues include escalating energy and raw material costs, lack of modernization, insufficient policy support, and workforce constraints.

Financial distress and shrinking market demand have significantly weakened the operational capability of most units.

Many stakeholders believe that without systemic interventions and proactive engagement from the government and financial institutions, closures are likely to continue.

SUGGESTIONS

Policy Reforms: Simplify regulatory compliance processes and introduce industry-friendly regulations. Provide targeted subsidies for energy usage and raw material procurement to reduce production costs.

Technology Upgrades: Facilitate access to modern machinery and automation tools through subsidized government schemes and public-private partnerships. Technical workshops and demonstration projects can help raise awareness and adoption.

Skilled Workforce Development: Launch region-specific training centers and vocational education programs in collaboration with technical institutes to address the skilled labor shortage. Offer incentives to youth and workers to enter the sector.

Financial Support: Establish industry-specific credit schemes with low-interest rates and flexible repayment options. Encourage banks to restructure existing debts and provide bridge financing to struggling units.

Market Revitalization: Promote the use of domestic castings through awareness campaigns and industry incentives. Encourage exports through simplified customs procedures, market linkages, and participation in global trade expos.

CONCLUSION

The foundry industry in Coimbatore, once a vibrant and critical contributor to South India's industrial economy, is currently facing a sustained and concerning decline. This study reveals that a combination of internal and external factors—including rising operational costs, outdated technology, labor shortages, regulatory hurdles, and weak market demand—have significantly impacted the sustainability of foundries in the region.

Through structured feedback from industry stakeholders, it is evident that foundry units are struggling to adapt to the changing industrial landscape. Many small and medium enterprises (SMEs), in particular, are unable to bear the financial pressure and lack the support needed to modernize their operations. The absence of proactive policy frameworks, limited financial aid, and the unavailability of skilled labor have compounded the crisis, leaving the sector vulnerable to further collapse.

The decline not only affects the foundries themselves but also has broader implications for employment, ancillary industries, and regional economic development. Thousands of workers who depend on this sector face job insecurity, while the slowdown in production affects

supply chains tied to automotive, agricultural, and construction industries.

Addressing these issues requires immediate, coordinated action. Government intervention in the form of tax incentives, easier compliance norms, and targeted financial support is essential. In addition, public-private partnerships can play a vital role in modernizing infrastructure, upgrading technology, and training the workforce. Institutions and industry bodies must also foster innovation, create knowledge-sharing platforms, and improve market access to restore competitiveness.

Reviving the foundry sector is not just about preserving the past—it is about reimagining its future. With the right strategies and collaborative efforts, Coimbatore's foundries can once again become a strong pillar of industrial growth, job creation, and regional prosperity.

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Appendix
Foundries Data
Questionnaire

1. What do you believe is the main reason for the recent closure of foundries?
 - A. Rise in raw material costs
 - B. Energy crisis or power shortages
 - C. Decline in demand from end-user industries
 - D. Government regulations or environmental norms
 - E. Labor shortage or unrest
2. Has the increase in energy costs affected foundry operations in your area?
 - A. Yes, significantly
 - B. Yes, slightly
 - C. No effect
 - D. Not aware
3. Were environmental regulations a factor in the shutdown of foundries?
 - A. Yes, directly led to closures
 - B. Contributed partly
 - C. Not a significant factor
 - D. Not applicable
4. How has the availability of raw materials (like scrap metal, coke, etc.) changed recently?
 - A. Severe shortage
 - B. Limited availability
 - C. No major change
 - D. Oversupply
5. Do you think global market conditions (e.g., exports, imports) influenced the closures?
 - A. Yes, significantly
 - B. Somewhat
 - C. Not at all
 - D. Unsure
6. Was labor availability a concern that contributed to shutdowns?
 - A. Yes, a major concern
 - B. Somewhat
 - C. No
 - D. Not relevant
7. How have government policies (e.g., taxes, permits, ESG regulations) impacted foundries recently?
 - A. Made operations difficult
 - B. Some impact
 - C. Helped operations
 - D. No impact
8. Has the cost of logistics and transportation increased for foundry-related supply chains?
 - A. Yes, significantly
 - B. Slightly
 - C. No change
 - D. Decreased
9. Do you think the closure of foundries is temporary or long-term?
 - A. Temporary due to market conditions
 - B. Permanent due to regulatory/economic shifts
 - C. Uncertain
 - D. Will vary by location
10. What is the biggest challenge foundries need to overcome to resume operations?
 - A. Energy and fuel costs
 - B. Policy support
 - C. Skilled labor
 - D. Market demand
 - E. Environmental compliance
11. How has the global supply chain disruption impacted foundry operations?
 - A. Caused major material delays
 - B. Increased costs
 - C. Both delays and cost issues
 - D. No impact
12. Were any foundries in your area closed due to compliance issues with safety or environmental standards?
 - A. Yes, Several
 - B. Few
 - C. None
 - D. Not Sure
13. Have recent geopolitical factors (e.g., international conflicts, sanctions) contributed to foundry closures?
 - A. Yes, significantly
 - B. To some extent
 - C. Not aware
 - D. No

14. How do you assess the role of technological upgrades (or lack thereof) in foundry shutdowns?

- A. Lack of modernization led to closures
- B. Upgrades were unaffordable
- C. Not a major factor
- D. Upgraded foundries remained competitive

15. Did seasonal weather conditions (e.g., extreme heat or flooding) influence recent closures?

- A. Yes, they halted operations
- B. Slight disruptions
- C. No impact
- D. Not applicable

16. Were financial losses or debt burdens key contributors to recent foundry closures?

- A. Yes, primary reason
- B. Contributed along with other factors
- C. Not significant
- D. Don't know

17. Have recent labor laws or wage regulations made it harder to run foundries?

- A. Yes, strongly affected costs
- B. Slight impact
- C. No impact
- D. Not applicable

18. Was there a drop in orders or demand from automobile or construction sectors?

- A. Yes, major drop
- B. Minor drop
- C. No change
- D. Demand increased

19. Do you think lack of government support (subsidies, tax reliefs) affected foundry viability?

- A. Yes, strongly
- B. Somewhat
- C. Not sure
- D. No

20. What support do you believe would help revive foundry operations?

- A. Energy subsidies
- B. Raw material price controls
- C. Easier credit or financing
- D. Policy reforms
- E. All of the above